
WEB SCALE DISCOVERY SERVICES IN LIS: A NEW PLATFORM FOR EFFECTIVE AND REMOTE ACCESS TO E-RESOURCES

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Abstract:

Libraries and Information Centres (LICs) are expected to offer library services with modern devices, create library and information products conducive to cater to the changing needs of students and offer both the library services and products in a way that will save their time in retrieval of relevant information and at the same time they will get access to all the resources available on one single platform. In this context, Web Scale Discovery services and its significance as a new platform for effective access to e-resources is explained in this article.

Key Words: *web scale discovery service, discovery service, index based discovery, E-resources, direct access to e-resources, library service.*

Introduction:

The main and central purpose of profession of librarianship is to provide useful information to users of library to satisfy them. In this context along with other library services, web scale discovery services need to be provided through libraries for effective use of e-resources. For libraries, Web scale discovery services are the services which are capable to search contents with index facilities from material of prompt and uncontrollable nature available either at local or remote place. With this service information resources can be made available as per sequence of requirement of user's community. Web scale discovery services brings together the books, e-resources in the form of either purchased or licensed contents which is of unlimited and scattered nature. This service plays a crucial role in policy work of libraries. With all available alternatives, selection of

alternative on the basis of experiences of readers is the most feasible solution to offer web scale discovery service.

Obstacles in Offering Web Scale Discovery Service:

1. Without indexing, the contents can be delivered effectively to users' community and the proper search strategy cannot be implemented for effective retrieval.
2. Content suppliers having copyright do not actively involve in such type of services and it becomes challenging to include them in web scale discovery services because publicly available search results are related with contents to be delivered to only registered users.
3. The sources are made available on the basis of subscription paid by libraries and selection of database. Only such resources are

made available under web scale discovery service.

4. Prevailing professional atmosphere related with web scale discovery services create so many complications. Because of many types of professional reasons, companies involved in providing content based subject index did not cooperate fully with suppliers of web scale discovery services.
5. Many of the content suppliers did not allow web scale discovery service providers to include their metadata related with their databases in their index.
6. It involves consideration of careful analysis of collection of libraries Vs the contents in the list provided through each service. It also becomes essential to think about how the web scale discovery services arrange for search results which are most suitable for readers.

Advantages of Web Scale Discovery Services:

1. Web scale discovery services provide helps to meet information needs and expectations of users and librarian's community.
2. It offers a common platform for all digital / electronic collections of the library and provide its access promptly to all users in shortest possible time through one window search facility.
3. It offers facility of filtering searched documents as per users search terms by author, subject, period, type of reading material viz. books, book chapter, journal article, conference proceeding etc. and the like. The distinctive features of web scale discovery services offer more effective research and learning outcomes

and thereby increases user's satisfaction.

4. The usage of E-resources can be increased to a considerable extent by connecting more users with all relevant contents involved in e-resources which consists of e-books, e-journals and e-databases.
5. It also provides the ability to deliver the necessary research support at the point of need in the digital environment.
6. Web scale discovery service is a one-stop solution with rich features to build a powerful and user-friendly digital library through which users can seamlessly access the digital resources anytime, anywhere and on any device.

Web Scale Discovery Service Providers in LIS:

Some of the important web scale discovery service providers are OCLC, EBSCO, ProQuest , Ex Libris , Knimbus etc. These are described in short as below:

1. OCLC:

This service is popularly known as WorldCat Discovery. *“WorldCat Discovery helps people easily find and get resources available at your library and in libraries worldwide through a single search of WorldCat and familiar, authoritative e-content collections. It also connects users to your collections via popular websites where people typically start their research”*. (<https://www.oclc.org>)

With this service, it is made possible to provide easy access to all kinds of resources stored at local and global level with smart searching facility.

2. EBSCO:

EBSCO discovery service and EBSCO host, by indexing open access journals researchers can get access to peer reviewed research and are able to search for the scholarly information that may support for their research. It provides access to quality content through leading technology to explore resources from books, e-books, audio books, journals, magazines and e-packages. It also offers subject specific resources covering all major resources.

“EBSCO discovery services adopts Access, Search, Choose and use pattern and combines the popular features of commercial websites with the functionalities necessary for libraries. EBSCO Discovery Service is more than a discovery tool. It is also a learning environment in which users are guided toward improving their search terms and finding items they may have overlooked otherwise.” (<https://www.ebsco.com>)

Its features and functionality includes sophisticated search with superior relevant ranking technology, direct access through the result list, full text, Intuitive interface, superior integrations of apps and integrations with multiple platforms and exceptional support from highly skilled staff.

3. Ex Libris: A ProQuest Company:

ProQuest owned Serials Solutions and Ex Libris to offer web scale discovery services. Ex Libris Prime with Primo and Summon provides web scale discovery services. Central discovery index, relevance ranking and exploration services are common features of these services.

Ex Libris packages are specially developed for making your library

stand out and to ensure that they are cloud ready. e.g. ‘cloud core’ through servers unify library workflows and provide speedy access to library resources, ‘Teaching Partner’ foster meaningful learning and enhance student’s success in online, on-campus and virtual learning environment, ‘Collection Plus’ enables access to contents needed by students. It is contributing a lot in the value of education and research by allowing academic institutions to create, manage and share knowledge.

Serials Solutions is a division of ProQuest and is part and parcel of web scale discovery service to manage e-resources by libraries.

Conclusion:

Web scale discovery are very important to retrieve relevant information from all available e-resources with the facility of seamlessly access to the digital resources anytime, anywhere and on any device. Hence, for online as well as off campus access to all such resources results in cost effective use of all resources. Beyond that, this service provides one stop solution for access to all e-resources subscribed by libraries through connecting more users with relevant content. The unique features of this service lead users to better research and learning outcomes and thereby libraries can justify their goal to satisfy readers community.

References:

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